

Effectiveness of YouTube Technologies in Sustaining Improved Academic Performance of Mathematics Students in Ogbia Educational Zone of Bayelsa State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This research work studied the ‘Effectiveness of YouTube Technologies in Sustaining Improved Academic Performance of Mathematics Students in Ogbia Educational Zone of Bayelsa State’. Mathematics teachers can use YouTube for lesson presentation on statistics and other concepts in mathematics as well as to post video clips and animations to students. Due to the nature of the study, the researcher used survey and a non-equivalent pre-test and post-test research designs. Purposive sampling technique was also used for the study; sample population of 600 was used out of 2,100 SS 11 mathematics students, from two public secondary schools in the educational zone under study. The instrument used was questionnaire and the researcher’s made Mathematics achievement test on Statistics concept. Data was analyzed using mean and independent t-test statistics. After carefully analyzing data obtained from the field, the researcher found out, among other things, that the use of YouTube can impact positively on the academic performance of Mathematics students when taught Statistics. Also, the SPSS computer analysis, P-value of 0.00 is less than the alpha level of 0.05 which means that it is significant. In other words, it shows that there is significant difference between the mean scores of students. Based on the findings and conclusion, the researcher recommended, among things, that mathematics teachers should encourage students to use YouTube instructional approach in learning Statistics).

Keywords: YouTube, Mathematics, Statistics, Online learning

Introduction

In the present dispensation, teachers have alternative teaching and learning approaches provided by the emergence of modern educational technology. The teacher uses different approaches and strategies to teach in order to make their learners active. One of the aims of Education is to inspire and enable individuals to develop their abilities to the highest potential levels throughout lifetime, so they can grow intellectually, well equipped for work, and be able to contribute meaningfully to the society and achieve personal fulfillment, thereby improving their knowledge and understanding for their own sake and to render the application of the knowledge to the growth of the economy and society. “Mathematics, the oldest of the sciences, is the abstract science of number, quantity, and space, either as abstract concepts (pure mathematics), or as applied to other disciplines such as physics and engineering (applied mathematics). It is the science and study of quality, structure, space, and change”. Mathematicians make out patterns, formulate new conjectures, and ensure that truth prevails through deduction from appropriate chosen axioms and definitions (Allahnana, Akande, Alaku and Alaku, 2022).

Mathematics is “the abstract science of number, quantity, and space, either as abstract concepts (pure mathematics), or as applied to other disciplines such as physics and engineering (applied mathematics). It is the science and study of quality, structure, space, and change” (Allahnana,

Akande, Alaku, and Alaku, 2022). Mathematicians seek out patterns, formulate new conjunctures, and establish truth by rigorous deduction from appropriate chosen axioms and definitions. Mathematics is the oldest of the sciences. It could be referred to as the abstract study of numbers, structures, space and change. It is on the basis of this that we say that mathematics is the bed rock of all Science subjects and is, therefore, needed for scientific and technological advancement of any nation (Olaf and Kai, 2010). Mathematics student uses numbers and signs to calculate fixed quantities or to compute variable quantities. It is the basis for precision in chemistry, astronomy and physics. Mathematics occupies a key position in Nigeria educational system and its application is in virtually all aspects of life (Ajit, 2018). Mathematics has ingredients for the effective articulation of the abstract elements of science that gives stimulating factors to the development of technologies. Not only that, Mathematics has become the central intellectual discipline of the technological society, and that as the society develops so will its quantitative aspects assume greater impact over its qualitative elements. Mathematical concepts are used in expressing the physical natural laws. Therefore, mathematics concepts and methods provide scientists with insight, into and about natural phenomenon (Anyo, 2016)

Mathematics has ingredients for realistic articulation of the abstract elements of science that gives stimulating factors to the development of technologies. Furthermore, it has become the central intellectual discipline of the technological society, and that as the society develops so will its quantitative aspects assume greater influence and dominance over its qualitative features. Mathematical concepts are used in expressing the physical natural laws. Therefore, mathematics concepts and methods provide scientists with insight, into and about natural phenomenon (Anyo, 2016). The present world of information and communication technology (ICT), has prompted alternative means of communicating curriculum content to learners in various subject areas including mathematics. There is now an emerging technology such as the YouTube. YouTube is a website that allow free video sharing and also to watch videos online. It allows one to create and upload videos online to share with others. YouTube being very popular has become one of the most used websites and a large resource tool for educational content. It is very easy and self-explanatory. It is not difficult to use YouTube. The poor performance has adverse effect in our collective effort in revolutionizing a sustainable tomorrow for the poor performance has adverse effect in our collective effort in revolutionizing a sustainable tomorrow for thriving green economy. (www.edudemic.com).

YouTube is an “online video-sharing platform that allows users to upload, view, share, and comment on videos” (Breslyn, 2022). In recent years, it has become a popular tool for students to access educational content, tutorials, and lectures. With the vast array of content available on YouTube, students can learn about practically anything, from basic algebra to complex. Most of the contents on YouTube is free, which means students can learn without spending money. This is particularly important for students from low-income backgrounds who may not have access to expensive course materials or resources. Both teachers and students have to access to diverse contents (Dickey, Tekkumru-Kisa, Yildirim, Kılıc, and Yildirim, 2016). YouTube has a wide range of educational content, both from recognized academic institutions and independent creators. This diversity allows students to access information on various subjects and topics, even those not offered in their schools or universities (Vikoo, 2013). It offers visual and interactive learning. This is to say that videos on YouTube are usually more engaging than traditional textbooks. Mathematics students studying Statistics can watch a video lecture, pause, rewind, and re-watch it at his or her own pace, making it an interactive experience. This can be particularly valuable for

visual learners who encounter difficulties in traditional lectures or course materials (Cigdemoglu and Ozsevec, 2016). YouTube technologies provide extra resources that are valuable to the scientific enterprise and in terms of syllabus, blog mentions, and presentations or scientific images (Thelwall, and Rezaie, 2010). Presently, science has been exploited greatly in coming up with great innovations to improve communication. On the other hand, some researchers still use nontraditional ways to generate curriculum content in Science Technology Engineering and Mathematics which do not meet the standards of evaluating information in the present information age. Mechanisms are really needed to promote, improve and sustain new ways in innovations in instructional delivery (Nkweke, 2003).

Lowensohn (2010) notes that in USA, just in one month, in May 2010 viewers of videos were approximately 14.6 million. The platform encourages the users to post music, legal and non-pornographic materials and other videos (Com Score, 2010). In the past criticisms have been raised on illegality of sharing content which is copyright TV programmes and other content) and most of them are popular but most videos are amateur videos. Majority of that content show cases of people engaging in uncommon activities everyday (Guzdial & Landry, 2008). YouTube provides opportunity for learning on schedule. This implies that, one of the significant advantages of YouTube is the ability to access content on-demand. There are no time constraints or schedules to follow. So, if the mathematics student contending with statistics needs to revisit a topic, he or she can always watch the video again, even several times, until he or she understands it. Collaboration and community: Finally, YouTube has a vibrant community of creators, educators, and students who share knowledge and support each other (Thelwall, Kousha and Rezaie, 2010). Through YouTube comments, students can interact with teachers, ask questions, and join in discussions. YouTube has become an increasingly popular platform for learning and education, and this is certainly true for statistics education as well. A number of studies have been conducted to investigate the relevance and effectiveness of YouTube in enhancing mathematics learning. For example, a study by Cigdemoglu and Ozsevec (2016) found that YouTube could be an effective tool for teaching mathematics concepts and enhancing student engagement, particularly for visual learners. The study suggests that the use of YouTube can help to provide students with a broader range of resources and perspectives, and that it can be particularly useful for difficult topics that require visual aids (Wood and Tiller, 2012).

The use of YouTube in teaching and learning in recent times is to enhance learning, create a balance between theory and practice of mathematics education, between the impacting of skills, the acquisition of techniques and knowledge, and between the growth and awareness of the students' personal response. YouTube not only serves as digital entertainment but also a great environment for learning and should be used in eLearning, which can truly benefit your eLearning audience. Furthermore, the mathematics students, when armed with knowledge of YouTube technology, the students can:

- i. Identify problems and needs in statistics
- ii. Formulate questions and design specification in statistics
- iii. Collect, select and organize information and contrast information on statistical concepts
- iv. Interpret information in statistics
- v. Search for solutions or designs which could be adapted to apply in problem solving in statistics
- vi. Research the potential social significance of the product/solution alternative
- vii. Undertake data analysis in research (MboniRuzea, and Sydney, 2021)

Most of the schools in Ogbia educational zone do not have well qualified mathematics teachers as well as relevant instructional materials to facilitate teaching and learning of Statistics. ICT has created valuable and advance methodology to resolve instructive matters and rising demand of requisite theoretical and practical knowledge by 21st century youth to support and, in fact prepare them for better tomorrow of mankind (Nkweke, 2012). YouTube websites make it possible for both teachers and students to view desirable videos in qualitative analysis. On the other hand, many underestimate the potential of YouTube as an educational tool. But YouTube could well be the most important educational tool of our time across gender.

Gender here constitutes characteristics of women, men, girls and boys that are socially constructed. This includes norms, behaviours and roles associated with being a woman, man, girl or boy, as well as relationships with each other. Being an issue that falls with the domain of social construct, gender differs from society to society and can as well change with time and space. Allahnana, Akande, Alaku, and Alaku (2018) posited that, gender refers to ‘socially constructed roles, behaviours, expressions and identities of girls, women, boys, men, and gender diverse people. It influences how people perceive themselves and each other, how they act and interact, and the distribution of power and resources in society’. Gender roles are influenced by the media, family, the environment, and society. In addition to biological maturation, children develop within a set of gender-specific social and behavioural norms embedded in family structure, natural play patterns, close friendships; and the teeming social environment of school life (Allahnana, Akande, Alaku, and Alaku, 2018).

The YouTube site provides students, teachers and qualitative research experts of both gender with a unique stock of videos that illustrates the concepts of basic qualitative research. (Duncan, Yarwood-Ross and Haigh, 2017) explain the importance of video sharing sites and argued that YouTube videos are valuable to practical, medical and clinical science education, and research. The authors report that the videos on YouTube may be used in a way that stimulates student participation, to counteract the students’ lack of interest often reported in traditional learning and forgetfulness. Most teachers of mathematics in public secondary schools in Ogbia educational zone may not have been aware of the potentials of YouTube during instructional development (MboniRuzea, and Sydney, 2021) hence, the researcher’s choice to investigate the effectiveness of YouTube on Academic Achievement of SS11 Mathematics Students in Ogbia educational zone of Bayelsa State.

Statement of the Problem

Over the years, there have been a lot of difficulties in accommodating students’ learning style in Statistics concepts in Mathematics, during instructional delivery. Students still find this concept as being abstract and complex hence their poor performance in examination as reported by the annual WAEC Chief Examiners Report (2018-2021). This has posed concern to most mathematics teachers, stake holders in education as well as policy makers in Nigeria. This report has over the time posed a concern in the poor academic achievement of SS 2 mathematics students. This therefore has made educators show interest in trying out other techniques and strategies that could facilitate the teaching and learning of mathematics concepts considered difficult by both students and teachers (Asikhia, 2022) Hence, the gap to be filled by investigating how YouTube instructional strategy can influence Mathematics students’ academic achievement and retention on Statistics in Ogbia educational zone of Bayelsa State. This consistent poor performance of students in mathematics in both internal and external examinations is the major reason this study is been

carried out, among other reasons, as to find out if mathematics teachers employed the use of YouTube technique during instructional development as part of effort to facilitate SS 2 mathematics students understanding and retention on Statistics.

Purpose of the Study

The main aim of the study was to undertake study of ‘Effectiveness use of YouTube Technologies in Sustaining Improved Academic Performance of Mathematics Students in Ogbia Educational Zone of Bayelsa State’. Specifically, it is to:

1. Determine the extent to which use of YouTube instructional delivery influences senior secondary school Mathematics students’ academic performance in Statistics
2. Determine if there is significant difference in mean scores of male and female senior secondary school Mathematics students taught Statistics using YouTube instructional techniques

Research Questions

The following two research questions guided the study:

1. To what extent is the use of YouTube influence senior secondary school Mathematics students’ academic performance in statistics?
2. Is there significant difference in mean scores of male and female senior secondary school Mathematics students taught Statistics using YouTube instructional techniques

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated and tested at .05 level of significance:

H01: There is no significant difference between mean scores academic achievement of senior secondary school Mathematics students taught Statistics using YouTube and those taught same concept with conventional teaching method

H02: There will be no significant difference in the mean scores of senior secondary school male and female Mathematics students taught Statistics using YouTube

Methodology

Due to the nature of the study, the researcher employed survey and a non-equivalent pre-test and post-test research designs to carry out this research on ‘Effectiveness of YouTube Technologies in Sustaining Improved Academic Performance of Mathematics Students in Ogbia Educational Zone of Bayelsa State’. The population for the study comprised of two thousand, one hundred (2,100) students from all the senior secondary school students that offer Mathematics in the educational zone of Ogbia educational zone of Bayelsa State, Nigeria. The sample population consisted of 600 senior secondary school mathematics students out of 2,100 students. And a purposive sampling technique procedure was adopted for the study, considering the nature of the research. The researcher made a reasoned to adopt this technique for the sake of convenience in selecting the number of research participants used for this study. The instruments for data collection were Questionnaire and Mathematics Achievement Test. The questionnaire, known as ‘Effectiveness of YouTube Technologies on Academic Performance Questionnaire (EYTAPQ), was structured on the four points Linkert scale of Strongly Agree (4), Agree (3), Disagree (2) and Strongly Disagree (1) and was used to answer the research questions while the Mathematics Achievement Test was on Statistics concept to address the hypotheses. The instruments were validated by two

mathematics lectures and two Educational Technologist from Federal University Otuoke, Bayelsa State. They effected necessary corrections or modification on the instruments. The reliability of the instrument was established using Peason Product Correlation statistics for estimating the internal consistency of the instrument. The outcome of the reliability test yielded a co-efficient index of 7.2 which was deemed fit to be used to proceed with administration of the instruments. Mean percentage was used to answer the research questions while, the independent sample t-test was used to test the null hypotheses.

Results

Research Question 1: To what extent is the use of YouTube effective in facilitating SS 1 Mathematics students’ academic performance in Ogbia local government area?

Table 1: Effectiveness of YouTube in Facilitating Senior Secondary School Mathematics Students’ Academic Performance in Ogbia Educational Zone.

S/N	Item	SA	A	SD	D	Total Score	Total No. of Resp.	Mean Score	Decision
		4	3	2	1				
1	Mathematics students are conversant with the use of YouTube in statistics learning	49	20	261	270	1048	600	1.7	Low
2	Mathematics students were not worried about learning via YouTube	30	20	270	280	1000	600	1.7	Low
3	Mathematics students perception of YouTube was positive	0	10	212	378	832	600	1.4	Low
4	Students prefer learning through lecture method	18	22	300	260	998	600	1.7	Low
5	Mathematics teachers assist their students find alternative means to study statistics	300	240	10	50	1990	600	3.3	High
6	Mathematics teachers made significant impact in aiding their students study online	25	25	400	105	1125	600	1.9	Low
7	Mathematics students often have data and collaborated with each other to learn statistics via YouTube method	15	48	301	236	1042	600	1.7	Low
8	Mathematics students initiated moves with their teachers to assist their them learn statistics through YouTube method	28	25	317	230	1051	600	1.8	Low
9	Mathematics students perceived the presence of ICT in learning Statistics as exciting and encouraging	261	309	20	10	2021	600	3.4	High
10	Management of secondary schools in Ogbia educational zone met Bayelsa state government to provide YouTube facilities for	15	50	266	269	1011	600	1.7	Low

	teacher s and students to ease students learning of Statistics								
11	Learning statistics through YouTube does not improve students’ academic performance	25	25	250	300	975	600	1.6	Low
12	Use of YouTube in teaching statistics can cater for individual learners peculiarities	280	260	0	60	1960	600	2.3	High
13	Students hardly learn statistics through YouTube	16	38	330	2161	504	600	1.8	Low
14	There is electrical power supply in Ogbia to support students use of YouTube facilities in learning statistics	0	20	300	280	940	600	1.6	Low
15.	Most mathematics students have lap top or android phones for learning statistics through YouTube	14	23	273	290	961	600	1.6	Low
16	Mathematics teachers do not resist use of YouTube for teaching statistics	30	30	300	240	1050	600	1.8	Low

(Source: Nkweke, 2003)

Looking at table 1 above, it showed that use of YouTube in teaching Statistics to SS 11 mathematics students was very negative and this had adverse effects on the students’ academic performance in statistics class

H01: There is no significant difference between mean scores academic achievement of SS 11 Mathematics students taught Statistics using YouTube and those taught same concept with conventional teaching method

Table 2: An Independent t-test Statistical Analysis of Mean Scores Academic achievement of Senior Secondary School Mathematics Students Taught Statistics using YouTube and those Taught same Concept with Conventional Teaching Method

Level	Alpha	N	Mean	Standard Deviation	Standard Error	t-Value	Df	P-(Sig./2 Tailed)
VAR0001	1.00	18	344.3333	83.44493	19.66814			
	0.05					-9.43	34	.000
VAR000	2.00	18	1285.9444	415.22771	97.87011			

(Source: Nkweke, 2003)

Looking at table 2 above, as shown in the SPSS computer analysis in table, P-value of 0.00 is less than the alpha level of 0.05 which means that it is significant. In other words, it shows that there is significant difference between the mean scores of the students.

Ho2: There will be no significant difference in the mean scores of senior secondary school male and female Mathematics students taught Statistics using YouTube

Table 3: A t-test Statistical Analysis of Students' Responses on Mean Scores of Senior Secondary School Male and Female Mathematics Students Taught Statistics using YouTube

Alpha Level	N	Mean	Standard Deviation	Standard Error	t-Value	Df	P-(Sig./2 Tailed)
VAR0001 1.00	18	334.0000	65.86450	16.46612	-8.41	30	.000
0.05							
VAR000 2.00	18	1191.1250	415.22771	100.44662			

(Source: Nkweke, 2003)

Looking at the table 3 above, it reveals that P-value (.000) is less than the alpha level (0.05) that means the null hypothesis is significant. This also means that there is significant difference between the mean scores of the male and female students' responses on Statistics in senior secondary school Mathematics in Ogbia Educational Zone of Bayelsa State.

Discussion of Findings

A study carried out by Amos Alunyo Bello (2018), found that YouTube could be used to supplement traditional teaching methods and enhance student learning outcomes in mathematics. The study suggests that YouTube can be particularly effective in promoting active student engagement, encouraging the development of problem-solving skills, and providing opportunities for self-directed learning. Another study by Dickey e(2016) found that the use of YouTube in chemistry education could be particularly useful for promoting student engagement and interest in the subject matter. The study suggests that the use of YouTube videos can help to make chemistry more interesting and relevant to students, and that it can be an effective way to spark student interest and curiosity (Anyor, 2016). Overall, these studies suggest that YouTube can be a relevant and effective tool for enhancing chemistry education and promoting student engagement and learning outcomes. YouTube has become an indispensable tool for students who want to supplement their learning with additional resources. However, while YouTube can be an excellent resource for studying, it should never be a replacement for traditional learning resources, such as textbooks and traditional lectures. Instead, it should be used as a complement to these resources to help enhance students' understanding and make learning more accessible and engaging (Moore, Gilmartin, and Kim, 2016). In the past research studies significant attention has been given to academic performance of the students. Factors like psychological, environmental personal, social and environmental were found to affect students' performance. These factors are different from country to country and also from individual to individual but they still affect the students' performances in respective countries. Factors like gender difference, socioeconomic factor, family educational background, teaching style, teacher education and class environment, determine the academic performance of any student. To evaluate performance of the student most researchers preferred to use World application of GPA to asses performance of the student anywhere (Cigdemoglu and Ozsevgec, 2016).

Conclusion

Mathematics is the abstract science of number, quantity, and space, either as abstract concepts (pure mathematics), or as applied to other disciplines such as physics and engineering (applied mathematics). Among other branches or aspects covered in mathematics is Statistics (a branch of

applied mathematics that deals with the collection, organization, analysis, interpretation, and presentation of data, the purpose of which is to solve problems related to scientific, industrial, or social matters. The present world of information and communication technology (ICT), has necessitated alternative means of communicating curriculum content to learners in various subject areas including statistics. There is now an emerging technology such as the YouTube. YouTube is a website that allow free video sharing and to watch videos online. It allows one to create and upload videos online to share with others. It is completely free resource that is available to our mathematics students in present dispensation to potentially use and facilitate learning of statistics and other concepts in mathematics. Unfortunately, most mathematics teachers in public secondary schools in Ogbia educational zone of Bayelsa State do not embrace learning statistics through YouTube due to lack of interest, lack of android/labtop computers, lack of data, internet problems, among other challenges. Consequence upon these, the situation led to poor performance of our mathematics students in both internal and external examinations. This academic downturn cannot make for collective effort in revolutionizing a sustainable tomorrow for thriving green economy in Nigeria nation polity.

Recommendations

Teaching and learning of Statistics in mathematics course, in the 21st century requires new approach occasioned by the emergence of 'Educational Technology, the New Science'. Various instructional strategies and techniques factored by educational information and engineering technologies, are now available, among which is YouTube technology that has capacity to facilitate mathematics students understanding of Statistics concepts. Mathematics teachers are expected to use this exciting technology, YouTube to accommodate individual learning style of the students, encourage scholastic attainment and retention, mastery learning, among other advantages of YouTube. Unfortunately, this dimension to modern instructional delivery is neglected at the face of high learner expectations from the teacher in present tines when there is need to reduce suffering and postpone death in African sub-region. To therefore stem this tide, the researcher put forward the following recommendations:

- i. Students of mathematics in public secondary schools in Ogbia educational zone of Bayelsa State should avail themselves of the rich opportunities offered by ICT to embrace learning of Statistics using YouTube technologies
- ii. Mathematics teachers in public secondary schools in Ogbia educational zone of Bayelsa State should encourage students to use YouTube technologies in learning Statistics for improve and sustain academic achievement, mastery learning, retention and recall
- iii. Bayelsa State government should provide internet facilities that will enable mathematics teachers and students access YouTube technologies for learning in the ICT age
- iv. Steady electrical power supply should be provided in Bayelsa State
- v. Bayelsa State government should provide mathematics teachers with either lap top or android phones as to enable teachers and students access YouTube instructional delivery
- vi. Bayelsa State government should provide security in places where internet facilities are installed to avoid being vandalize by hoodlums

- vii. Mathematics teachers and students should be exposed to workshops on the use of YouTube technology in teaching and learning of Statistics
- viii. Mathematics teachers should plan their statistics lesson very well before engaging the students in YouTube learning with instructional objectives well stated and followed
- ix. Mathematics teachers in Ogbia educational zone should ensure proper evaluation of the teaching – learning process as to achieve their lesson objectives in Statistics
- x. Bayelsa State government should provide mathematics students with bursary to help them have money to buy data since it is difficult to access the internet without data
- xi. Educational information and engineering technologies in collaboration with instructional material technicians should be employed to provide special support system in mathematics education in Ogbia educational zone, in Bayelsa State, Nigeria.

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